

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN INCREASING THE SPEECH COMPENSATION OF PRIMARY STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7951929>

Annotation: didactic games differ in their form in one way, both from creative games, which are played mainly in kindergarten, and from games, where the teacher himself descends by telling a story and strengthens the students as a result of asking them one by one.

Keywords: elementary class, task, didactic games, competence, speech, reader, opinion

One of the main tasks of primary education is to grow the speech of students. The fact that speech cultivation is carried out in three directions: working on a word, working on a vocabulary and a sentence, working on connected speech is noted in the methodological literature.

Speech is not only a means of expressing a thought, but also a weapon of its formation. Thought acts as the psychological basis of speech, while the condition for its cultivation is thought enrichment. Speech can be successfully cultivated only on the basis of mastering the system of mental activity. Therefore, when growing students' speech, great importance is attached to the types of work that focus on preparing, improving the material, choosing, placing the relevant one on the topic and logical thinking.

Thinking grows successfully if it is formed and articulated orally using language material. The concept is represented by words or combinations of words, so that it becomes an important material of communication in a word that is a means of language. When a person knows a word (a combination of words) that represents a concept, he will have the opportunity to think in External speech, based on this concept

Not only do elementary students use techniques such as memorizing their speech, explaining or retelling the meaning of words, but the use of games, which are interesting activities for them, is of great help in achieving the desired, high results. Because small school-age students occupy the main place in their activities. Depending on the age and psychological characteristics of children, the game is the main tool in understanding the world and the self, in the cultivation of bound speech.

From teaching children the game, a certain educational goal is envisaged. This is also the most important importance of the game. The forms and methods of conducting the game differ from other types of Education.

Didactic game methods are endless, there is an opportunity to repeat and change, add various innovations to it. For example, we spent 5-7 varieties of the game "silence" with the whole class, as well as with some children, repeating more than 10 times, "what has changed?" type match was played with 5 different types of instructional material. The result allows the game qualifications to be uniform and robust and to be able to listen to and follow each rule of the game.

Didactic games differ in their form in one way, both from creative games, which are played mainly in kindergarten, and from games, where the teacher himself descends by storytelling and strengthens students as a result of one-on-one requests. Didactic games serve the task of teaching and are conducted at an interesting, interesting, understandable level. Children train with John-dili for the purpose of winning, Get used to the fact that they will definitely complete each given task, as a result of which there is a middle interest in completing didactic tasks. Didactic games help to better understand the purpose of each lesson, the goals and objectives of each exercise.

Didactic games include the exhibitionism of education, the teacher's speech and the movement of children, as a result of which unity is born in perception (in the signs of vision, hearing, skin sensation). This encourages the teacher to think about what the children say and express what is said, that is, to fulfill the rules of the didactic game themselves.

In the lesson, we can see several didactic games in which students participate with excellent interest.

Didactic game "story". The teacher writes a few words on the writing board. Maslan: like Nafisa, clock, rain, book. Readers independently compose a story with the participation of these so. In this, along with the increase in their vocabulary wealth, the correct composition of sentences, the correct pronunciation of sounds, the shell of creative and independent thinking are formed. The teacher encourages active participants from time to time, gaining confidence in the students and encouraging them to be active from this. These games can also be easily used in extracurricular activities and clubs.

The game "talk salt from mixed given words"

The words written on the cards are shuffled to make the game happen. Students form a sentence instead of words. To make the game easier, whichever word the sentence begins is distinguished from the others. Whoever makes a correct and quick sentence is the winner of the game. It can be played both between groups and one on one. This game can be used frequently. To do this, two, three envelopes are issued to each team, taking several envelopes. Inside each envelope there will be a card of words representing one sentence. Which group constructs sentences quickly and correctly is the winner of the game.

For example:

Manbaidir	Kitob	Bilim	
baxt	Keltiradi	mehnat	
Yo'q	Aqldan	Boylik	ortiq
Bir	Bilimsiz	Yashar	
Bilimdon	Yashar	Ming	

Find the lost piece of talk

In elementary grades, the section and second-order pieces are studied determinant, complement, case is referred to by the term second-order pieces with a common name in one whole point. Thanks to this, it is possible to conduct a series of grammatical games on the

location of the choice of all sentence fragments. Throughout the game, students learn the function of sentence fragments, their interrogations, the connection of words. Learns the usual order of sentence fragments. In order to host the game, the owner is given sentences that have been dropped. The reader must write the EGA selectively. The owner is given along with the words in several pieces.

1..... an excellent student at the school.(Planet, Comilaga, Abdullah, Sherzodni

2..... he received a grade of "5" in his mother tongue lesson.(reader, reader, reader, reader) < BR >

Such a game can be played both among classroom students and between groups.

Ditactic game "journey".

Students are instructed to describe a path from school or their home that is a specific joygcha. Students independently observe the "object" for several days and describe it verbally. In this game tool, which requires meticulous attention, elegance, observation, attention to the environment, attention to the chorus, it is possible to cultivate feelings of love for the motherland, love for nature, attention to the chorus. In addition, when using these games, the speech of students develops, the vocabulary wealth increases even more, the qualification of independent thinking is formed.

The above educational games serve to facilitate and strengthen the process of mastering knowledge, as well as increase the activity of students in the lesson, to create an interesting organization of each activity aimed at growing speech.

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